

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18314501>

BALNEOLOGICAL RESOURCES AND ISSUES OF THEIR USE

Sobirjonov Muhammadkarim Mahmudjon o'g'li

National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

ABSTRACT

Currently, one of the important tasks is the study of the main regularities of the formation of balneological resources, the development of theoretical foundations for their rational use, assessment of their impact on public health and reduction of negative consequences, as well as conducting research aimed at improving the environmental situation.

As a result of the increase in the amount of harmful substances emitted by man into nature, chemical compounds accumulate in the environment, and the number of various diseases increases significantly as a result of air, water, and soil pollution and poisoning. In the treatment of such diseases, balneological resources are of great importance. In our republic, there are many natural inorganic mineral waters, therapeutic mud (peloids), sand, caves, salts, and balneological resources with therapeutic properties in natural climatic conditions. Increasing the effectiveness of treatment using balneological resources, protecting them from pollution and deterioration requires separate scientific research.

Currently, issues of balneological resources and their rational use, as well as scientific research aimed at improving the ecological situation, are of great importance. In this regard, research aimed at the rational use and protection of balneological resources based on the identification of natural geographical factors and patterns of their formation and distribution in the context of global climate change is of current importance.

Keywords: *balneological resources, mineral waters, peloids, sand, natural climatic conditions, cave, salts, physical properties, ions, criterion, classification.*

INTRODUCTION

It is known that since ancient times, people have widely used balneological resources with healing properties - natural inorganic mineral waters, thermal springs, therapeutic mud, sand, caves, salt, and natural climatic conditions for health restoration and treatment.

The term “balneology” (Latin "balneum" - bathing and Greek "logos" - teaching) was first used at the end of the 18th century (c. 1783) by the Swiss physicist and physician Jacob Blanchard in his textbook "The Use of Mineral Waters and Springs for Healing Purposes."

Balneological resources - elements of the natural environment with therapeutic properties for the human body - natural inorganic mineral waters, thermal springs, therapeutic mud, sand, caves, salt, and specific climatic conditions, etc. "Balneology" is a field of science that studies the healing properties of these resources and develops methods for their use.

Balneological resources are abundant on Earth, including in our country, and they are classified according to several factors, such as physical properties, chemical composition, and healing properties.

Classification - (from Lat. *classis* - class, rank, and *facio* - I separate, divide, stack) one of the methods of systematization, ordering, the division or unification of objects of one category into classes based on features that distinguish them from objects of another category and are more characteristic of objects of this category.

The main part of balneological resources consists of minerals of inorganic composition. They are diverse in chemical composition, physical properties, and temperature indicators.

Some general classifications of balneological resources:

1. **Balneological mineral waters:**

By chemical composition, mineral waters are subdivided into different types depending on their main mineral composition:

Calcium-magnesium bicarbonate waters are rich in calcium, magnesium, and bicarbonate ions, which have a calming and anti-inflammatory effect.

Sulfate waters contain high levels of sulfate ions and are often used for detoxification and purification properties.

Chloride waters are rich in chloride ions, which are used for antiseptic and purifying properties.

Sodium bicarbonate waters are rich in sodium bicarbonate and have a calming effect on the digestive system.

Hydrogen sulfide waters contain high amounts of hydrogen sulfide and are used for their vasodilating and anti-inflammatory effects.

Radonated water is called medicinal water if it contains a radioactive chemical element - radon (inert gas).

Based on the chemical composition, other groups of balneological mineral waters are distinguished in the following table (*Table 1*).

Table 1

Groups of balneological mineral waters by chemical composition

№	Group	Main ions and composition	Characteristics and medical applications
1.	Hydrocarbonate	HCO_3^-	Beneficial for the gastrointestinal tract, kidneys, and urinary tract
2.	Sulfate	SO_4^{2-}	Beneficial for digestive system, liver and lungs
3.	Chloride	Cl^-	Improves blood circulation and nervous system function
4.	Calcium	Ca^{2+}	Increases the strength of bones and teeth, has an anti-allergic effect
5.	Magnesium	Mg^{2+}	Beneficial for the nervous system, muscles, and cardiovascular system
6.	Sodium	Na^+	Normalization of blood pressure affects the nervous system
7.	Iodine	I^-	Improves thyroid function, strengthens immunity
8.	Bromine	Br^-	Calms the nervous system, helps against stress and insomnia
9.	Silicon (silicate)	H_2SiO_3	Improves skin condition, has anti-inflammatory effect
10.	Radon	Rn	Used in the treatment of arthritis, joint and muscle diseases
11.	Hydrogen sulfide	H_2S	Recommended for dermatology, treatment of skin diseases

Note: The table was compiled by the author based on the books "Mineral Waters and Therapeutic Use" by V.P. Nefyodov and "Resortology and Balneotherapy" by A.A. Alekseev.

Mineral waters are often used in sanatoriums and hospitals, recreation areas for balneotherapy (therapeutic bathing), drinking therapy (treatment with drinking water),

and various treatments aimed at improving health. Such waters are used for medicinal purposes in several regions of the world (*Table 2*).

Table 2

Countries with extensive use of mineral waters

№	Country name	Popular mineral water resorts	Composition of mineral water	Treatment directions
1.	Germany	Baden-Baden, Wiesbaden, Bad Kissingen	Sulfate, bicarbonate, thermal	Joints, digestive, nervous system
2.	France	Vishi, Evian-le-Bene, Kontrekseville	Hydrocarbonate-calcium-magnesium	Gastrointestinal system, kidneys
3.	Italy	Salsomadjore-Terne, Fuji, Bano-Vinoni	Iodine, sodium, hydrogen sulfide	Skin improvement, endocrine system
4.	Czech Republic	Karlovy Vary, Mariánské Lázně, Františkov Lázně	Hydrocarbonate-sulfate-sodium	Hepatobiliary system, diabetes, kidneys
5.	Russia	Kislovodsk, Pyatigorsk, Yessentuki, Zheleznovodsk	Sulfate, sodium bicarbonate	Cardiology, gastrointestinal, nervous system
6.	Hungary	Budapest (Gellert, Sechenyi), Havi	Radonic, thermal, sulfate	Rheumatology, orthopedics, skin treatment
7.	Japan	Beppu, Hakone, Kusatsu	Hydrogen sulfide, iron, carbonate	Arthritis, nervous system, skin diseases
8.	Spain	Caldas de Malavella, Ardena, Mondariz	Sulfate-calcium-magnesium	Stress, skin treatment, muscle relaxation
9.	Switzerland	Bad Ragaz, Loèche, Salsouge	Silicon, thermal, bicarbonate	Osteochondrosis, nervous system, cardiovascular
10.	Georgia	Borjomi, Sairme, Nabeglavi	Sodium bicarbonate, carbonate	Gastrointestinal system, kidneys, metabolism

Note: The table was compiled by the author based on the books "Balneotherapy: Evidence-based Clinical Practice" by K.Sukenik and "Resortology" by A.A.Alekseev, as well as on the Internet.

2. Balneological thermal waters.

Thermal waters are classified differently depending on their temperature, they can be cold, warm, hot, and very hot. Water temperature can have a healing effect on the human body. Thermal waters are used to boost blood circulation, relax muscles, and relieve pain.

Thermal waters are classified according to their temperature into the following groups (*Table 3*).

Table 3

Groups of thermal waters by temperature

№	Group	Temperature (°C)	Characteristics and effects
1.	Hypothermal	< 20	Good for the gastrointestinal system, kidneys, oral and therapeutic
2.	Warm (Mesothermal)	20–34	Helps relax the nervous system and muscles, widely used in spa treatments
3.	Moderately warm (Indifferent)	34–37	Since it is close to normal body temperature, it has a mild effect on the cardiovascular system and nerves.
4.	Hot (Thermal)	37–42	Used for the treatment of joint and muscle diseases, improves blood circulation
5.	Extremely hot (Hyperthermal)	> 42	Treats the skeletal muscular system, skin, accelerates blood circulation, but is not recommended for patients with heart disease

Note: The table was compiled by the author based on information from electronic websites and the Internet.

Thermal waters are formed naturally as a result of geothermal activity and are distributed in various regions of the world. They are commonly found in geosynclinal regions where mountain-building processes are rapidly occurring - the Pacific Ring of Fire, the Alpine-Himalayan geosynclinal zone (*Table 4*)¹.

¹ *Note: Table WHO (World Health Organization) and baden-baden.com, thermesdevichy.com, termedisaturmia.it, karlovyvary.cz compiled by the author based on data from websites such as.*

Table 4

Countries with extensive use of thermal water

№	Country name	Popular resorts	Water composition	Water temperature (°C)	Treatment directions
1.	Germany	Baden-Baden, Wiesbaden, Bad Kissingen	Sulfate, bicarbonate	47–68	Joints, digestive system, nervous system
2.	France	Vishi, Evian-le-Bene, Kontrekseville	Hydrocarbonate -calcium-magnesium	14–60	Gastrointestinal system, kidneys, metabolism
3.	Italy	Saturnia, Abano-Terme, Iskya	Hydrogen sulfide, iodine, sodium	37–80	Skeletal-articular system, skin improvement, endocrine system
4.	Czech Republic	Karlovy Vary, Mariánské Lázně, Františkov Lázně	Hydrocarbonate -sulfate-sodium	30–73	Hepatobiliary system, diabetes, kidneys
5.	Russia	Kislovodsk, Pyatigorsk, Yessentuki, Zheleznovodsk	Sulfate, sodium bicarbonate	20–60	Cardiology, gastrointestinal system, nervous system
6.	Hungary	Budapest (Gellert, Sechenyi), Havi	Radonic, thermal, sulfate	30–76	Rheumatology, orthopedics, skin treatment
7.	Japan	Beppu, Hakone, Kusatsu	Hydrogen sulfide, iron, carbonate	40–100	Arthritis, nervous system, skin diseases
8.	Spain	Caldas de Malavella, Ardena, Mondariz	Sulfate-calcium-magnesium	35–56	Stress, skin treatment, muscle relaxation
9.	Switzerland	Lakerbad, Bad Ragaz, Sankt Gallen	Silicon, thermal, bicarbonate	32–51	Osteochondrosis, nervous system,

					cardiovascular system
10.	Georgia	Borjomi, Sairme, Nabeglavi	Sodium bicarbonate, carbonate	17–38	Gastrointestinal system, kidneys, metabolism

These thermal waters have long been protected for their healing properties and have often been used as health resorts and resort-health centers.

Thermal waters are widely used for medicinal purposes in various parts of the world. Some popular areas include (*Table 4*):

These places often have resort establishments offering treatments such as balneotherapy (healing bathing), mud baths, and various resort therapies using the healing properties of thermal waters.

3. Peloids (clay and mud):

Peloids are natural clays or muds rich in minerals and organic matter. They are classified according to their mineral composition as follows:

Sulfur-rich peloids are clays with a high content of sulfur (S), used for anti-inflammatory and skin treatment.

Silicon-rich peloids, clay with high silicate dioxide (SiO₂), are used for skin exfoliation (a regular procedure that removes dead skin cells and exposes new, young cells) and renewal.

Therapeutic peloids are used for therapeutic purposes in various regions of the world, in particular in areas famous for natural hot springs or mud deposits. Some of the sights include the following (*Table 5*)¹.

Table 5

Countries that make extensive use of therapeutic peloids

№	Country name	Popular resorts	clay	Type of clay	Treatment directions
1.	Hungary	Haviz, Harkan		Sulfide, rich in organic matter	Joints, rheumatism, nervous system
2.	Italy	Abano-Terme, Montecatini-Terme		Volcanic, thermal mud	Skeletal muscular system, arthritis
3.	Russia	Taman, Saki, Starorusskiy resort		Sulfide, peat	Dermatology, Orthopedics, Gynecology

¹ Note: Table heviz.hu, abanotherrae.it, minzdrav.gov.ru, thermes-dax.com, goturkiye.com, saki-crimea.com created by the author based on the data of such electronic sites.

4.	France	Daks, Aix-le-Ben	Sulfide, thermal clay	Cardiovascular system, nervous system
5.	Spain	Mar Menor, Arcenae	Volcanic, rich in minerals	Stress, muscle relaxation
6.	Germany	Baden-Baden, Bad Kissingen	Hydrothermal mud	Gastrointestinal system, rheumatism
7.	Czech Republic	Treplitz, Karlov Var	Sulfide, radioactive element	Skeletal muscular system, nervous system
8.	Turkey	I'm from Dalaman, Pamukkale	Volcanic, mineral component	Arthritis, dermatology, nervous system
9.	Ukraine	Saki, Berdyansk	Sulfide, mineral	Gynecology, orthopedics, nervous system
10.	Georgia	Shaltubo, Sairme	Radioactive element minerals	Diseases of joints, nervous system

4. Balneological caves:

Contains natural elements such as mineral waters, gases, or microclimate, characterized by healing properties and having beneficial effects on the human body due to unique environmental conditions. People visit balneological caves for respiratory procedures, skin diseases, and general recreation.

Balneological caves are classified according to the following characteristics:

Air quality: there may be high levels of certain gases (such as radon) or specific ionization in the air inside the caves, which positively affects the functioning of the respiratory organs.

Microclimate: Caves can create a stable microclimate characterized by stable temperature, humidity, and air circulation.

Mineral composition: the walls or floors of some caves contain healing minerals or mineral waters that can be absorbed or inhaled through the skin.

Balneological caves are natural underground environments that are usually beneficial due to a unique microclimate that includes stable temperature, humidity, and air composition. These caves are often used for speleotherapy, where patients spend time in a cave environment to improve their health, which is especially beneficial for respiratory illnesses such as asthma and allergies.

Some popular places where balneological caves are used for healing purposes include the following (Table 6)¹.

Table 6

Countries where healing caves (speleotherapy) are common

№	Country name	Popular healing caves	Healing properties	Location
1.	Ukraine	Soledar Salt Cave,	Nervous system, respiratory tract, allergy	Eastern Europe
2.	Poland	Truskaves cave	Respiratory tract, asthma, immunity boosting	Central Europe
3.	Germany	Velichka Salt Cave	Bronchitis, asthma, skin improvement	Central Europe
4.	Russia	Berchtesgaden Salt Cave	Speleotherapy, respiratory diseases	Eastern Europe
5.	Austria	Beryozovsky Salt Cave,	Allergy, bronchitis, nervous system	Central Europe
6.	Hungary	Ust-Kachka Cave	Skin diseases, nervous system	Central Europe
7.	Czech Republic	Obertauern Cave	Strengthening immunity, respiratory tract	Central Europe
8.	Slovakia	Budapest Hayvis Cave	Respiratory problems, asthma	Central Europe
9.	Romania	Salt cave of Zlate-Gori	Spellotherapy, bronchial asthma	Eastern Europe
10.	Kyrgyzstan	Domitsa Cave	Fresh air, nervous system, circulation	Central Asia

These caves attract visitors seeking natural remedies for respiratory diseases, as the conditions inside alleviate symptoms and improve overall respiratory function.

4. Balneological sands:

These are natural or specially prepared sands, which are used for therapeutic purposes. These sands are often used together with mineral waters or independently, in hot or cold conditions, as a therapeutic remedy. Balneological sands are mainly rich in minerals and may contain sodium, magnesium, calcium, silicon, iron, iodine, and other

¹ Note: Table solotvyno.com.ua, speleotherapy.info, salzheilstollen.de, domica.info created by the author based on the data of such electronic sites.

useful elements. The healing properties of these sands depend on their chemical composition, physical structure, and heat retention capacity.

Mineral composition: balneological sand often contains minerals and elements beneficial for skin and general health, often silicate ($(\text{SiO}_x(\text{OH})_{4-2x})_n$), calcium (S), magnesium (Mg) and potassium (K) etc.

Thermal properties: some balneological sands are located in geothermal active areas that can naturally heat the sand. This thermal aspect can enhance its healing effect, especially when treating joint and muscle pain.

Therapeutic use: balneological sand is used in various therapeutic programs, including sand baths, where patients are buried in heated sand to rest and improve blood circulation. Due to its mineral composition, it can also be used for peeling (cleaning the face) and treating the skin.

Balneological sands are usually located in specific geographical locations known for their natural deposits of healing sands. For example, beaches near springs of volcanic origin or rich minerals are their common sources.

Balneological sand, referring to sand with specific mineral composition and properties used in therapeutic procedures, is used for therapeutic purposes in several parts of the world. These sandy areas are usually associated with natural hot springs or mineral-rich sands that provide healing benefits. Some popular places where balneological sand is used (*Table 7*).

Table 7

Extensive than balneological sand (psammotherapy - sand treatment) countries to use

No	Country name	Popular healing sandy areas	Healing properties	Location
1.	Egypt	Siwa Oasis, Western Desert	Arthritis, rheumatism, muscle and joint disorders	North Africa
2.	Morocco	Sahara Barchan (Merzuga)	Diseases of the nervous system, stress, skin	North Africa
3.	Tunisia	Desert Salt, Sahara	Circulatory disease, skin	North Africa
4.	UAE	Liva dunes	Body cleansing, toxin removal	Middle East
5.	Turkmenistan	Kyzylkum and Karakum Deserts	Skeletal muscular system, nervous system	Central Asia

6.	Kazakhstan	Moynak Sand Territory, Aral Sea Region	Joint and skin diseases	Central Asia
7.	Chinese	Badin-Jaran Desert	Circulatory, nervous system	East Asia
8.	Mauritania	Saharan sands	Warm-up, Toxin Release	West Africa
9.	Namibia	Namib Desert (Sossusvley)	Nervous system, immune enhancement	South Africa
10.	Uzbekistan	Kyzylkum Desert	Joint diseases, skin diseases	Central Asia

Note: The table is compiled by the author based on data from Clinical Rehabilitation, World Health Organization reports on traditional medicine use in North Africa and Central Asia, Journal of Ethnopharmacology.

These places are especially attractive to visitors seeking natural remedies for skin diseases, joint pain, and healing. Sand baths are often combined with other resort treatments to enhance their healing effect.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODS

When conducting research on balneological resources, a number of methods and materials are used. It is necessary to note the research work of many scientists on the identification of new sources of mineral water and the development of methods for their effective use.

The first chemical analysis of spring water was carried out by Fischer in 1814.

P. Savenko (1828), F. O. Konradi (1831), N. E. Drozdov (1839) described springs known from the 16th-18th centuries and a number of new mineral water sources. Regime observations and studies of the chemical composition of the waters of the Mashukskiy, Buguntinskiy, Zheleznogorskiy, Kislovodskiy, and Berezovskiy springs were conducted. Issues of their origin will be considered.

In 1863, S. A. Smirnov opened the first scientific balneological society in Pyatigorsk, where scientific writings and works forming the basis of scientific balneology were published.

In 1931, N.S. Zvonitsky published a scheme for the classification of mineral waters based on the principles adopted at the 4th Hydrogeological Resort Meeting. This classification was based on the relationship of waters depending on the composition of

the six main ions in them. In 1932, at the 4th Hydrogeological Resort Meeting, based on the fundamental principles put forward by E.E. Carstens, V.A. Alexandrov proposed a classification of mineral waters. In it, all mineral waters are divided into six classes according to ionic composition, the presence of balneologically active ions, and gas composition.

In 1948, A.M. Ovchinnikov published the work "Basic Principles of Zoning of Mineral Waters of the Caucasus," in which, based on the systematization of large analytical materials, he established the regularities of the distribution of individual types of mineral water deposits in the Caucasus. He formulated the basic principles of the doctrine of mineral waters.

In 1964, V.V. Ivanov and G.A. Nevraev published a classification of groundwater with some changes widely used to characterize mineral waters.

In 1955, K. Grum published the work "A Complete Systematic Practical Description of Mineral Waters, Therapeutic Mud, and Bathing in the Russian Empire."

In 1969, the map of therapeutic mineral waters of the USSR, the catalog of mineral waters of the USSR, and an appendix to the map of mineral waters of the USSR were published. This map, catalogue, and appendix represent the whole and describe the underground mineral healing waters.

In 1968, a map of medicinal clay at a scale of 1:800,000 was published, and in 1970, a catalog of clay deposits in the USSR was published. In the works of L.S. Mikheev and Ya.A. Trebuhov (1975), data were summarized; special studies on therapeutic mud, methods and main mud exploration work, issues of assessing therapeutic mud reserves, and management of therapeutic muds were considered.

In the 1970s, A. D. Pliny, in his work "History of Nature," mentions the existence of "a land that heals all wounds" about Parasin (present-day Saki) on the Crimean Peninsula.

In 1972, G.S. Vartanyan and L.A. Yaroski published a manual "Exploration and Assessment of Operational Reserves of Mineral Water Deposits." In 1974, carbonated waters of the Borjomi type were discovered in the Nagut hydrogeological area.

In 1977, the book "Mineral Waters" by E.V. Posokhova and N.I. Tolstykhin was of great importance, which for many years was the main textbook on mineral waters.

In 1995, G.V. Kulikov, A.V. Zhevlakov, and S.S. Bondarenko published the reference book "Healing Mineral Waters of the USSR."

N.A. Kenesarin and M.M. Krilov, N.N. Khojiboev, A.N. Sultonkhodzhaev, A.S. Khasanov, S.M. Mirzaev, U.U. Umarov also made great contributions to the development of hydrogeological science in Uzbekistan, including the fields of mineral hydrology. In this regard, he authored several manuals, such as M.M. Krylov's "Dynamic Balance of Groundwater in the Irrigated Regions of Uzbekistan and

Methods of its Study," N.N. Khojiboev's "Hydrogeological-Meliorative Regionalization" (1968), A.N. Sultonkhodjaev's "Fergana Artesian Basins" (1972), and "Metallogeny of the Artesian Basins of Central Asia" (1992).

In our republic, there are not many studies conducted in this area. Nevertheless, information on the rational use and protection of balneological resources based on the identification of natural geographical factors and patterns of their formation and distribution in the context of global climate change can be found in the research works of Sh.Sharipov, M.Gudalov [*Sharipov et al., 2020*].

In revealing the significance of balneological resources in the development of tourism in foothill and mountainous regions, the research work of Sh. Sharipov and Sh. Shomurodova is of great importance. [*Sharipov et al., 2020*].

Also, the necessary information can be obtained from the research works of K. Bekanov on mapping areas with balneological resources using GIS technologies [*Bekanov et al., 2020*].

The main part of the numerous balneological resources located in the territory of Central Asia belongs to the Aral Sea basin. Information about this basin can be found in the research works of R. Ibragimova et al. [*Ibragimova et al., 2019*].

It is known that the emergence, distribution, and change of balneological resources occur under the influence of natural and anthropogenic factors. Data on the influence of anthropogenic factors on the change of balneological resources are highlighted in the works of Z.Tojjeva et al. [*Tojjeva et al., 2024*].

The climatic characteristics of the regions also serve as an important indicator in determining the state and quality of balneological resources. Such research works were carried out by I.Turdimambetov, F.Murgas, F.Victor, M.Oteuliev, A.Madreimov, G.Shamuratova, S.Atabaev and A.Reymov [*Turdimambetov et al., 2024*].

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Areas with balneological resources have been found in countries famous for their natural springs or mineral deposits and used for their healing effects on human health. It is advisable to include Uzbekistan among the countries famous for their balneological resources.

The first information about the balneological resources of the territory of Uzbekistan can also be found in the works of our great scientists. They left valuable information about the origin, composition, physicochemical properties, distribution, evaluation criteria, and healing properties of balneological resources.

Abu Ali Ibn Sina noted in his work that "the chemical composition of groundwater is formed depending on which rocks it flows from." He explained mineral waters to

patients as healing waters and thereby laid the foundation for the science of "hydrogeochemistry."

Abu Rayhan Beruni was able to correctly explain the origin and properties of artesian waters even at that time. In his works, he writes: "If the area of groundwater supply is located above the earth's surface, that is, in the mountains, they boil from the bottom of the well and flow to the surface. If the supply area is located below, they will not reach the surface."

In general, Abu Rayhan Beruni correctly described the reasons for the formation of springs, the rise of groundwater to the surface (artesian water), and its inflow. He analyzed the issues of the formation of the chemical composition of groundwater and was at the forefront of his contemporaries in this regard.

In the 19th-20th centuries, expeditions organized by Russian scientists and many specialists in the natural sciences included in them comprehensively studied the natural conditions, geological structure, ground and surface waters of our homeland, and ways to use them for their own purposes.

E.A.Eversman, who was part of the Russian diplomatic mission in 1820, F.F.Berg and E.I.Eikhvold in 1824-1825, and F.I.Baziner and G.Danilovsky, who were part of the Russian expedition in 1842, wrote works on the geology and groundwater of the Kyzylkum Desert, the Mangyshlak Peninsula, and the Ustyurt Plateau.

During this period, special scientific expeditions were organized to study the hydrology of Central Asia, which included specialists in various sciences and fields. These expeditions were led by P.P. Semenov-Tyan-Shansky, A.P. Fedchenko, N.S. Seversev, A.F. Middendorf, I.V. Mushketov, V.F. Oshanin, V.A. Obruchev, and L.S. Berg.

In 1950, B.A. Bader, in his research "Treatmental Properties of Mineral Waters," collected information about the healing waters of Central Asia.

According to the classification of V.V. Ivanov and G.A. Nevraev, mineral waters are divided into 7 balneological groups (A, B, C, G, D, J, Z):

- A - waters that do not have specific substances and properties;
- B - carbonate, dissolved carbonate-gas waters;
- V - sulfide (hydrogen sulfide) waters;
- G - radon waters;
- D - iodine, bromine, and iodine-bromine waters;
- J - iron waters;
- Z - siliceous waters.

These groups are also classified according to their gases, chemical composition, and mineralization.

By composition, gases are divided into nitrogenous, nitrogen-methane, methane, and carbon dioxide groups.

By chemical composition: hydrocarbonate, sulfate, chloride.

The main part of the above-mentioned mineral waters is widespread in nature, and they are hot and saline waters with low and high mineralization. Below, we will consider some balneological groups of mineral waters distributed in Uzbekistan.

Sulfide (hydrogen sulfide) natural waters. Such waters have various mineralizations and are considered the most valuable and healing among mineral waters in terms of physiotherapy. Sulfide waters found in nature are divided into: weak sulfide (10.0-50.0 mg/l), medium sulfide (50-100.0 mg/l), strong sulfide (100-250.0 mg/l), very strong sulfide (above 250.0 mg/l). The ionic composition of sulfide mineral waters depends on hydrogeological conditions and occurs together with hydrocarbonate, sulfate, and chloride group mineral waters. In nature, waters with low mineralization (from 5 g/l) to high mineralization (above 35 g/l) contain gases such as methane, nitrogen, and trace elements such as iodine, bromine, and magnesium. Most often, their formation is associated with the formation of oil and gas deposits. For example, sulfide waters in the Fergana Valley were formed in oil and gas storage structures. Sho'rsuv, Changara, Chimgan, Polvontosh, Andijan, Xo'jaobod, and Janubiy Olamushuk are considered sulfide mineral waters. Their composition is diverse, and their balneological properties increase depending on the concentration of iodine, bromine, boron, and other substances. When taking a mineral water bath, all its components positively affect blood circulation through the skin, the nervous system, and improve metabolism.

Radon waters. It is less common in nature. If water contains a radioactive chemical element - radon (inert gas), it is called radon-containing medicinal water. Besides radon, there can be various gases and salts. Many radon waters are hot, low-mineralized, and are considered healing in the treatment of many diseases. Depending on the radon content, mineral waters are classified as weak radon (5.0-40.0), medium radon (40.0-200.0), and high radon (above 200). For example, the water in the Akhangaran River and the Orashon spring is considered radon-containing mineral water. The water is hot (37°C), sulfate-sodium, low-mineralized (2.3 g/l), radon (45 mg/l), silicon (90 mg/g).

Waters containing large amounts of iodine and bromine, or bromine-iodine waters, are widespread in nature. If the water contains 25.0 mg/l of bromine and 5.0 mg/l of iodine, it is called bromine-iodine mineral water and is widely used in hospitals. Iodine-bromine artesian basins are also present in many parts of the Earth (Western Siberia, Fergana, etc.).

Iodine-bromine waters. Iodine, bromine, and bromine-iodine waters have been found in the underground water basins of Bukhara, Karshi, and Surkhandarya. In the Bukhara-Karshi groundwater basin, iodine and bromine waters with high concentrations accumulate more. It flows from underground wells, with a very low water discharge (1 l/sec) and a temperature of 26-46°C. The dissolved gases in its composition are methane-nitrogen and methane. Water contains 7-50 mg/l of iodine, up to 650 mg/l of bromine and iron. Such mineral waters are mainly beneficial for diseases of the nervous system, musculoskeletal system, gastrointestinal tract, female genital organs, skin, and radiculitis.

Ferruginous mineral waters. Although iron-containing mineral waters are low and moderately mineralized (20 mg/l of iron), they are classified as medicinal mineral waters and are widely used in some hospitals. Iron waters appear in nature in waters between rocks and have various ionic and gaseous, sometimes metallic compositions such as magnesium, aluminum, zinc, nickel, copper, lead. Depending on the concentration of iron oxide, mineral waters are divided into iron (20-40 mg/l), bitter iron (40-100 mg/l), and very bitter iron (above 100 mg/l). In the territory of the Aktashsay valley of the Tashkent region, ferruginous waters, which turned out to be springs, were discovered. The water is clean and clear, has a characteristic iron taste, and its temperature ranges from -4-15°C.

Siliceous mineral waters. Siliceous mineral waters are used in quantities exceeding 50 mg/l. They were found at depths (from 800 to 1350 m) in areas such as Chukurkul, Central Kagan, and West Tashli in the Kashkadarya region. The water flow rate in wells ranges from 0.1 to 1 l/sec, temperature from +44°C to +65°C. The water contains elements such as sulfate-chloride, sodium chloride, iodine, bromine, and iron. Siliceous mineral waters were produced in the territory of the Ahmad Yassavi mahalla of the Upper Chirchik district of the Tashkent region. The water composition is chloride-sulfide-sodium, mineralization 2.8 g/l. The amount of silicic acid in it is 74 mg/l, the temperature is +61 °C. This water is used in the balneo-physiotherapeutic hospital named after Ahmad Yassavi for the treatment of various diseases.

Medicinal peloids. Various therapeutic muds are also used in resorts and other conditions. In nature, therapeutic muds are formed under the influence of climate, geological, biological, and other natural factors. Mineral particles, plant and animal remains, and microorganisms on land and in water, as a result of chemical and biochemical processes, have become components of therapeutic mud.

In Egypt, India, and Central Asia, healing mud has been used since ancient times for the treatment of various diseases. In Russia, the healing effect of mud was known in the 15th century, and it was used to treat certain diseases. Due to the in-depth study

of the therapeutic properties of mud, it is now widely used in many sanatoriums of our country.

Sanatoriums use therapeutic mud to treat diseases of the musculoskeletal system (specifically the spine, joints, muscles), nervous system, gastrointestinal, vascular, skin, and gynecological diseases. Therapeutic muds have a comprehensive (chemical, biological, thermal) effect on the body. Medicinal muds are often used in hospitals together with mineral waters. Examples of this are Chartak, Chinabad, and a number of balneological hospitals of our republic.

Therapeutic muds are divided into several types: peat, sapropel, sulfide, and sulfide-clayey. Sulfide-clayey clays are common in Uzbekistan and its surrounding areas. Large reserves of sludge have been discovered in the Jizzakh region (Baliqli and Tuzkon), Karakalpakstan (Muynak), and the Khujand region of Tajikistan (Akhsukon). They originated mainly in terrestrial lakes.

Many therapeutic muds are rich in sulfides, various salts, and trace elements. Clays have low (less than 2-5 g/l) and high (more than 150 g/l) mineralization. They can also have different ion compositions and temperatures.

Therapeutic mud is supplied to sanatoriums and hospitals in the Fergana Valley, Tashkent and Jizzakh regions from the lakes of Akhsukon and Balykly.

Lake Balykly is located in the Arnasay district of the Jizzakh region (30 km from the city of Jizzakh, 200 km from the city of Tashkent). The shape of the lake is long, the shores are very low. Length 2 km, width up to 1-1.8 km, area - 2.06 km². The bottom of the lake is flat, bowl-shaped; the water entrances are disturbed. The thickness of the sedimentary silt is 0.1-0.2 m. From the bank to the center, the thickness of the silt increases uniformly (4.5-5 m). Mud reserves are about 177,500 m³. The surface of the silt is covered with salt to a thickness of 5-10 cm. It consists of 80-90% mirabilite and sulfate-sodium salts.

Famous balneological centers widely used for medicinal purposes in Uzbekistan are presented in the following table (*Table 8*).

Table 8

Popular sanatoriums in Uzbekistan

№	Sanatorium name	Location	Main therapeutic factors	Treatable diseases
1.	Handbag	Fergana region	Sulfide mineral waters and mountain air	Atherosclerosis, complications of phlebitis and thrombophlebitis, skin and female diseases

2.	Shahimardan	Fergana region	Mineral waters and mountain air	Diseases of respiratory tract
3.	Kyzyltepa	Fergana region	Sulfate-hydrocarbonate sodium waters	Diseases of digestive, musculoskeletal, nervous and cardiovascular systems
4.	Chartaq	Namangan region	Sodium minerals and thermal, hyperthermal, iodine, chloride, calcium-sodium minerals	Diseases of the musculoskeletal system, nervous system, digestive system, gynecological and cutaneous
5.	Kasansay	Namangan region	Clear-air mountain climate and composition of sulfate-chloride, bicarbonate-sodium natural mineral water	Diseases of cardiovascular, musculoskeletal, nervous system and respiratory tract
6.	Flower garden	Namangan region	Iodine-bromine, chloride-sodium-magnesium-calcium, metaboric acid waters	Diseases of the musculoskeletal system, gastrointestinal tract, gallbladder and bile ducts, gynecological and cutaneous
7.	Seedling	Namangan region	Sodium chloride, weakly iodized alkaline waters and galvanic sludge	Diseases of the urinary tract, digestive system, musculoskeletal system, and nervous system.
8.	Southern Mole	Andijan region	Iodine, bromine, iron, lithium chloride and sulfate-chloride waters	Diseases of the nervous system, musculoskeletal system and skin
9.	Wrestler	Andijan region	Bromine, chloride-sodium, very hot, saline mineral waters	Diseases of cardiovascular, nervous system,

				musculoskeletal system and skin
10.	Khojaabad	Andijan region	Iodine, bromine mineral water	Diseases of stomach, skin, kidneys
11.	Charvak	Tashkent region	Clean mountain air and mineral waters	Cardiovascular, nervous system, muscular diseases
12.	Zaamin	Jizzakh region	Clean mountain air and mineral waters	Diseases of cardiovascular system, respiratory tract and nervous system
13.	Baliqli and Tuzkon	Jizzakh region	Sulfide-silty mud	Diseases of musculoskeletal system and skin
14.	Obibola	Navoi region	Natural clay, thermal waters	Inflammatory diseases of joints, bones, skin
15.	Oksokota	Surkhandarya region	Geothermal hot water (65-70°C), sulfate-calcium-sodium	Arthritis, osteochondrosis, skin diseases
16.	Kumkurgan	Surkhandarya region	Mineral water for drinking, magnesium-calcium, sulfate	Diseases of stomach, liver, intestines, kidneys
17.	Gazelle house	Surkhandarya region	Chloride-calcium-sodium, highly mineralized hydrogen sulfide waters	Diseases of musculoskeletal system, nervous system and skin

These sanatoriums, with their unique natural healing factors, are effective in treating various diseases. Each sanatorium has its own characteristics and treatment directions, which patients can choose according to their needs.

In Lake Balykly, located in the Arnasay district of the Jizzakh region, there is a therapeutic mud consisting of various salts, a sample of which was subjected to chemical and physicochemical, as well as X-ray fluorescence analysis in the analytical chemistry laboratory of the National University of Uzbekistan, and the following chemical analysis results were obtained.

Chemical analysis results

Table 9

Mass of the delivered sample

№	Sample mass, g
1.	10.5896
2.	10.1952
3.	10. 3199
4.	10.4200

10 g of the sample was weighed, placed in a 100 ml beaker with 1:1 HCl, and boiled thoroughly on a water bath for 1-2 hours. In this case, the metals are dissolved in the form of chlorides.

Table 10

Mass remaining in the precipitate and dissolved in solution

№	Total mass, g.	Precipitate, g	Solution, g
1.	10.5896	3.8988	6.6908
2.	10.1952	4.8020	5.3930
3.	10. 3199	4.8461	5.4731
4.	10.4200	4.7279	5.6921

Table 11

Silicon percentage

№	Total mass, g.	SiO₂ %
1.	10.5896	36.81%
2.	10.1952	47.10%
3.	10. 3199	46.66%
4.	10.4200	45.37%

Table 12

Results of qualitative analysis for metals

(V.N. Alekseev course on chemical qualitative analysis by the semi-micrometod)

T/r	1	2	3	4
K ⁺	-	-	-	-
NH ₄ ⁺	-	-	-	-
Ag(I)	-	-	-	-
Hg(I)	-	-	-	-
Hg(II)	-	-	-	-
Pb(II)	-	-	-	-
Ca(II)	+	+	+	+
Al(III)	+	+	+	+
Co(II)	+	+	+	+
Cu(II)	+	+	+	+
Ni(II)	+	+	+	+
Fe(III)	+	+	+	+
Zn(II)	+	+	+	+

Physicochemical analysis

1) Electrical conductivity (measured on a conductometer):

1 sample - 11,5

2 sample - 5,67

3 sample - 3,99

4 sample - 5,94

2) pH value (pH in meters):

1 sample - 8,27

2 sample - 7,50

3 sample - 7,09

4 sample - 7,85

Results of X-ray fluorescent element analysis

Analyzed result

Page 1/2

Sample Information

Sample name	Balchiq
File name	Balchiq
Application	Umumiy.
Date	2023/ 5/19 11:30
Analyzed by	
Counts	1
Comment	

Analyzed result(FP method, Scatter)

No.	Component	Result	Unit	Stat. Err.	LLD	LLQ
1	Cl	3.39	mass%	0.0037	0.0019	0.0058
2	Br	0.0023	mass%	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0002
3	Mg	3.26	mass%	0.0335	0.0454	0.136
4	Al	2.72	mass%	0.0153	0.0164	0.0491
5	Si	13.0	mass%	0.0182	0.0017	0.0052
6	S	8.53	mass%	0.0079	0.0021	0.0063
7	K	1.01	mass%	0.0070	0.0033	0.0098
8	Ca	10.0	mass%	0.0191	0.0106	0.0317
9	Ti	0.199	mass%	0.0018	0.0018	0.0053
10	V	(0.0022)	mass%	0.0005	0.0015	0.0046
11	Cr	0.0041	mass%	0.0002	0.0005	0.0016
12	Mn	0.0321	mass%	0.0009	0.0017	0.0051
13	Fe	1.68	mass%	0.0032	0.0011	0.0034
14	Co	(0.0055)	mass%	0.0007	0.0021	0.0064
15	Ni	0.0018	mass%	0.0001	0.0003	0.0009
16	Cu	0.0030	mass%	0.0001	0.0002	0.0005
17	Zn	0.0053	mass%	0.0001	0.0001	0.0003
18	Ga	0.0009	mass%	<0.0001	0.0001	0.0004
19	As	0.0004	mass%	<0.0001	0.0001	0.0004
20	Se	0.0006	mass%	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0002
21	Rb	0.0063	mass%	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0002
22	Sr	0.0802	mass%	0.0002	0.0002	0.0006
23	Y	0.0018	mass%	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0003
24	Zr	0.156	mass%	0.0011	0.0004	0.0012
25	Mo	0.0033	mass%	0.0005	0.0010	0.0029
26	Ag	0.0007	mass%	<0.0001	0.0002	0.0006
27	Sn	0.0020	mass%	0.0001	0.0003	0.0008
28	Ba	0.0334	mass%	0.0008	0.0015	0.0045
29	Ir	(0.0008)	mass%	0.0002	0.0004	0.0012
30	Pb	0.0018	mass%	<0.0001	0.0002	0.0005
31	Fr	(0.0003)	mass%	<0.0001	0.0003	0.0008
32	Eu	0.0326	mass%	0.0021	0.0051	0.0154
33	U	0.0012	mass%	<0.0001	0.0002	0.0007

Analyzed result

Page 2/2

Sample Information

Sample name Balchiq
 File name Balchiq
 Application Umumiy.
 Date 2023/ 5/19 11:30
 Analyzed by
 Counts 1
 Comment

Spectrum

Analysis of the oxide content of X-ray fluorescent elements

No.	Component	Result	Unit	Stat. Err.	LLD	LLQ
1	Cl	3.39	mass%	0.0037	0.0019	0.0058
2	Br	0.0023	mass%	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0001
3	Fr	(0.0003)	mass%	<0.0001	0.0003	0.0008
4	MgO	5.42	mass%	0.0549	0.0754	0.226
5	Al2O3	5.14	mass%	0.0287	0.0310	0.0929
6	SiO2	27.9	mass%	0.0365	0.0037	0.0110
7	SO3	21.3	mass%	0.0189	0.0053	0.0158
8	K2O	1.22	mass%	0.0084	0.0040	0.0119
9	CaO	14.0	mass%	0.0263	0.0148	0.0445
10	TiO2	0.332	mass%	0.0030	0.0029	0.0088
11	V2O5	(0.0057)	mass%	0.0009	0.0026	0.0079
12	Cr2O3	0.0065	mass%	0.0004	0.0008	0.0024
13	MnO	0.0418	mass%	0.0012	0.0020	0.0061
14	Fe2O3	2.40	mass%	0.0045	0.0016	0.0048
15	Co2O3	(0.0082)	mass%	0.0010	0.0030	0.0091
16	NiO	0.0023	mass%	0.0002	0.0004	0.0012
17	CuO	0.0038	mass%	0.0002	0.0002	0.0006
18	Ga2O3	0.0013	mass%	<0.0001	0.0002	0.0005
19	ZnO	0.0066	mass%	0.0002	0.0001	0.0004
20	As2O3	0.0005	mass%	<0.0001	0.0002	0.0005
21	SeO2	0.0009	mass%	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0002
22	Rb2O	0.0069	mass%	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0002
23	SrO	0.0946	mass%	0.0003	0.0002	0.0007
24	Y2O3	0.0023	mass%	<0.0001	0.0001	0.0004
25	ZrO2	0.211	mass%	0.0015	0.0006	0.0017
26	MoO3	0.0050	mass%	0.0008	0.0014	0.0043
27	Ag2O	0.0007	mass%	<0.0001	0.0002	0.0006
28	SnO2	0.0025	mass%	0.0002	0.0003	0.0010
29	BaO	0.0373	mass%	0.0009	0.0017	0.0051
30	Ir2O3	(0.0009)	mass%	0.0002	0.0004	0.0013
31	PbO	0.0020	mass%	<0.0001	0.0002	0.0005
32	Eu2O3	0.0372	mass%	0.0024	0.0060	0.0181
33	U3O8	0.0014	mass%	0.0001	0.0003	0.0008

Table 14

Allowable amount of substances

№	Name of the substance	Found amount mg/kg	Maximum permissible amount mg/kg
1.	Cl	33900	-
2.	Mg	32600	36000
3.	Al	27200	300000
4.	Si	130000	-
5.	S	85300	160
6.	Ca	100000	10
7.	K	10100	2140
8.	Cr	41	6
9.	Mn	321	1500
10.	Fe	16800	40000
11.	Co	55	5
12.	Ni	18	4
13.	Cu	30	55
14.	Zn	53	23
15.	Pb	20	32

In the sample taken from the Fish Lake, the content of sulfur, chromium, cobalt, nickel, and zinc exceeds the established norm. Some of the elements listed above belong to the category of heavy elements.

CONCLUSIONS

During the writing of the article, the following conclusions can be drawn regarding the research topic under study and the work carried out on this topic.

Information was studied on the analysis of classification groups that differ from each other depending on a number of factors, such as the emergence of the term balneology, physical properties, chemical composition, and therapeutic properties of balneological resources, as well as on the study of the main patterns of their formation and the development of theoretical and methodological foundations for their rational use. From these data, attention was paid to the important aspects of the research work, and brief descriptions were given.

Based on the analysis of classification groups, it was established that balneological mineral waters, thermal springs, therapeutic mud (peloids), sand, and

their distribution in certain geographical areas depending on climatic conditions and the main natural geographical patterns of their formation correspond to other similar regions. Based on the data collected from the studied works, tables with various classifications were compiled.

The first information about the balneological resources of the territory of Uzbekistan can also be found in the works of our great scientists. They left valuable information about the origin, composition, physicochemical properties, distribution, evaluation criteria, and healing properties of balneological resources. The study of these data and their effective use are of great importance in increasing the level of research work.

REFERENCES

1. Sharipov, S.M., Gudalov, M.R., Shomurodova, S.G. (2020). Geological situation in the Aydar-Arnasay colony and its atrophy. *Journal of Critical Reviews*. DOI: 10.31838/jcr.07.03.85.
2. Sharipov, S.M., Shomurodova, S.G., Gudalov, M.R. (2020). The use of mountain kars in the tourism sphere in the resort and recreation zone of Chimgan-Charvak. *Journal of Critical Reviews*. DOI: 10.31838/jcr.07.03.87.
3. Ibragimova, R.A., Sharipov, S.M., Abdunazarov, U.K., Mirakmalov, M.T., Ibraimova, A.A. (2019). Aral Physical and Geographical District, Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan. *Asia Life Sciences*, 1,227235.<http://www.scopus.com/inward/record.url?eid=285081208836&partnerID=MN8TOARS> .
4. Zulkhumor Tojiyeva, Kamola Omanova, Nodirbek Pardayev, Nizomiddin Jaloliddinov, Bekzod Musayev and Sadridin Khursanov. Regional Characteristics in the Dynamics and Location of the Rural Population of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *E3S Web of Conferences* 491, 04004.
5. Bekanov et al., (2020) Application of geoinformation technologies and remote sensing to detect land use and changes in the soil cover caused by the drying up of the Aral Sea. *Periodico Tche Quimica*, 17 (36), pp. 390-401.
6. Turdimambetov I., Murgaš F., Victor F., Oteuliev M., Madreimov A., Shamuratova, G. Atabayev S. Reymov A. (2024). Measurement of environmental indicators of the quality of life in a region with extreme climatic conditions. Evidence from around the Aral Sea. *Geojournal of Tourism and Geosites*, 57 (4spl), 1941-1951. <https://doi.org/10.30892/gtg.574spl08-1361>.
- a. Александров В.А. Живая вода. М.: Мысль, 1982. - 127 с.
7. Большой глоссарий терминов международного туризма/ под. Ред.

М.Б.Биржакова, В.И.Никифорова.- СПб.: «Издательский дом Герда», 2006.- 936 с.

8. Иванов В.В., Невраев Г.А. Классификация подземных минеральных вод. - М.: Недра, 1964. - 167 с.

9. Куликов Г.В., Жевлаков А.В., Бондаренко С.С. Минеральные лечебные воды СССР. - М.: Недра, 1991. - 399 с.

10. Смирнова А Я., Бочаров В.Л. Минеральные воды России. - Воронеж: РЦ Менеджер, 1996. - 132 с.

11. Широкова В.А. Пресные и минеральные воды Сарепты. Природа. № 8, 2006.- С.31 -36.

12. Царфис П.Г. География природных лечебных богатств СССР: (Курортологические аспекты). - М.: Мысль, 1986. - 237с.

13. Посохов Е.В., Толстихин Н.И. Минеральные воды (лечебные, промышленные, энергетические). Л.: Недра, 1977.-240 с.

14. Капуста Л.И. Марциальные Воды. Страницы истории первого русского курорта. СПб.: «Дмитрий Буланин», 2006. - 100 с.

15. Бедер Б.А., Салтейская Э.Я., Хасанов А.С. Минеральные и термальные воды. В монографии “Гидрогеология СССР. Узбекская ССР”, том XXXIX. “Недра”, М.:1971.

16. Zokirov A.Z. "Healing Resources and Medical Centers of Uzbekistan." Tashkent. Ibn Sina - 1997.

17. Sobirjonov M.M. "The Development of Initial Knowledge in Europe on Healing Waters and Their Use." / Geographical Science and Digital Economy: Problems and Prospects. / Materials of the International Scientific-Practical Conference. - Namangan, 2023. pp. 137-139.

18. Sobirjonov M.M. "Types of Balneological Resources and their Classification." / Integration in modern geographical research: problems and solutions. / Materials of the International Scientific-Practical Conference. - Тошкент, 2021. 147-149.

19. Sobirjonov M.M. "The Development of Initial Knowledge on Therapeutic Mineral Waters and Their Use in Uzbekistan." / The role of modern geoinformation cartography, remote sensing methods, and technologies in geographical research. / Materials of the International Scientific-Practical Conference. - Тошкент, 2021. Pp. 509-512.